

EMBEDDING MICROMACHINES IN MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

We have recently demonstrated that composites with unique properties can be manufactured by embedding many small, passive, simple machines in a matrix. We have been referring to these as Machine Augmented Composites (MAC). The simple machines modify the forces inside the material in a manner chosen by the material designer. Multifunctionality is obtained when traditional fibers give the material strength and stiffness and the machines add additional properties. The MAC concept and the results of both theoretical and experimental studies will be described. Potential applications will be described, such as clamping mechanisms, fasteners, gaskets, seals, and vibration damping.

KEY WORDS

Composite Machines Stress Conversion Damping Fastener

INTRODUCTION

For over 50 years, composite materials have been made by embedding fibers or particulates in a matrix material. For fiber-reinforced composites, fibers supply special properties such as strength and stiffness to the composite while the matrix material holds the fibers in place and transfers loads among them. Even though the fibers and matrix materials retain their own identities, combining them results in a composite that takes on the fiber's unique mechanical properties because of the large number of embedded fibers contained within the composite. Further, since the embedded fibers are very small in size, the composite can be milled, drilled and otherwise processed as if it were a homogenous material. These attractive properties foster the use of fiber-reinforced composites in a wide range of applications in virtually every industry.

In this paper we describe the development of a new type of composite material in which the fibers are replaced by simple machines. Machine-augmented composites (MAC) are a new class of composite materials that utilize the tailored shape of embedded machines to create unique mechanical properties [1]. Rather than using traditional cylindrical fiber reinforcements, the embedded machines are versions of these reinforcements, tailored to specific machine shapes chosen by the material designer, from which innovative properties can be obtained. The geometry of the machines modify the composite's internal forces passively, creating as many different mechanical properties as there are possibilities for the cross-sectional shapes of machines. When the machines are densely packed within a matrix, these machine-augmented composites (MACs) reflect the properties of the machines just as the fiber-reinforced composites reflect the properties of fibers. The presence of the machines allows the composite to have mechanical properties that are not currently available with traditional materials. MACs can easily be fabricated (for example, using extrusion, rapid prototyping) and can be scaled easily. At the same time, these machines can be made small enough to allow post-processing in ways similar to that of other composite and homogeneous materials.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the cross section of a simple stress-conversion machine that converts shear forces into tensile/compressive forces and vice versa. This machine consists of two parallel (horizontal) plates connected through two struts (slanted walls) situated at an angle to the plates (Z-type configuration). Note that if shear forces are applied to the machine as shown, the slanted walls change their angle, forcing the top and bottom plates to move apart. This movement causes compressive forces on any adjacent contacting material. Conversely, if compressive forces are applied to the top and bottom faces, the machine imposes shear forces on any abutting material. As indicated in the figure, this machine responds to shear forces with a tensile/compressive strain.

(Figure 1) Schematic of a simple Stress-Conversion.

Embedding these machines in a matrix allows the resulting composite to convert compressive forces to shear forces and vice-versa. There are many cases where an object may have shear forces imposed upon it. If the object were manufactured with a machine augmented material, the stress-conversion machines could cause them to expand and wedge more tightly in position. This stress conversion property could be used in the design of fasteners or clamping devices. In addition, seals or gaskets may be able to be made more effective if machines were incorporated into their design. For other applications, we have been exploring using these machines in adhesive joints to reduce peel stresses. We also have preliminary data showing how cracks are diverted when they approach a machine because the stress field is altered.

Embedding the Z-shaped mechanisms in a matrix creates a material that distorts in shear when it is displaced in compression and vice versa. This stress conversion property is not unique to this material. Off-axis unidirectional composites similarly convert stresses but introducing machines in the matrix allows a wider range of property variations and simplifies the manufacturing process. This allows design engineers to use a new method to solve mechanical issues. In cases where shear forces are present in the composite, it will expand or contract depending on the orientation of the shear force. This expansion can be a benefit to the designer.

MACHINE SIZE CONSIDERATIONS

The optimal machine size is a trade-off between the homogeneity of the mechanical properties and the manufacturing cost. The homogeneity issue involves the size of the machine relative to the size of the part. The mechanical properties of the MAC may be degraded or severely non-homogeneous if the machines are not “small” with respect to the final part. The severity of this effect can be estimated from theoretical studies of the mechanical response of a composite containing elements smaller than the unit cell. One recent study [2] has shown that “the error associated with replacing the smallest-scale regions by an equivalent homogeneous medium is very small, even when the ratio between the length scales is as low as three.” This study indicates that as long as a given length (unit cell) of composite contains more than three machines, it will have properties that approach those of a homogeneous material. In general, this consideration favors the smallest possible (or practical) machine size.

A second factor that favors smaller machine’s sizes is the desire to post-process the MAC in the same manner in which traditional composites are processed. One must be able to drill, form, and bolt the MAC with little consideration as to where the machines are within the material. These

considerations support the requirement that the machines need to be “small” with respect to the size of the part.

Both of the preceding arguments lead to the conclusion that the machines should be as small as possible. Conversely, an argument that favors larger machines involves the ability to manufacture the machine using reasonable manufacturing methods. Assuming that typical composite manufacturing techniques are to be utilized, it is reasonable to assume that the machines will be the most costly component of the composite. The total machine cost is simply the number of machine elements times the cost of each. Consequently, the cost of the material can be minimized by using fewer, larger machines. In addition, larger machines are typically less expensive because standard manufacturing methods can be employed.

In summary, cost considerations favor the larger machines and the desire for homogeneity favors smaller sizes. Using these considerations, the fabrication, experimental and analytical discussions will use machines with a cross section of 1-mm, unless otherwise noted. A machine with a cross section of 1-mm is much smaller than most finished parts, yet not so small that it cannot be made by inexpensive manufacturing procedures.

FABRICATION

A MAC material has been manufactured using 1-mm machines (see Figure 2). The machine’s walls are angled 60-degrees from the bottom. Long segments with this cross section were extruded out of nylon. Nylon is ideal for this application because it is easy to extrude, is compatible with many polymeric matrix materials, and has good mechanical properties.

The processing steps incorporating these machine segments into a composite were patterned after current composite practices. The extruded machine segments were laid down, side-by-side, and adhesively bonded to a polyester scrim cloth. This assembly represents one ply of machines. The ends of the machines were sealed with an adhesive. The plies then were stacked on top of each other and placed in a mold. To produce a composite laminate, the stack was impregnated with a room-temperature-curing polyurethane resin matrix material and placed in an evacuated bell jar to outgas the polyurethane as it polymerized and hardened.

The optical micrograph shown in Figure 3 was taken from a thin slice of the material that was placed between crossed polarizers to highlight the difference between the machines and the matrix. The machines are made out of nylon and are hollow. The polyester scrim cloth that was placed between the plies of the machines as a manufacturing aid are evident in the figure. Each machine measures 1-mm

(Figure 2) Scanning electron micrograph of the prototype simple machines.

(Figure 3) Optical micrograph of three plies of stress-conversion MAC material.

on a side and extends through the length of the composite material. As can be seen from this cross section, a volume of the resulting composite material is approximately 40% machines and 60% matrix. A higher machine-matrix ratio is possible.

EXPERIMENT

When put in compression, this stress conversion material should distort and produce shear stresses.

Unfortunately, there is no ASTM test for this property: the faces of a standard testing machine would constrict the material's movement so that it could not be able to displace in shear. To remedy this problem, we developed a unique experimental set-up (Figure 4) that we utilize to measure lateral or shear displacement as a function of compressive displacement. Two samples are prepared and set on top

(Figure 4) Experimental set-up used to measure shear displacement as a function of compressive load and displacement.

of one another in a mechanical testing machine. The samples are rotated 180-degrees with respect to each other and placed in a double-lap configuration with a metal loading tab placed between the two samples. In this arrangement, neither sample subjects the testing machine to shear forces. When the top sample pushes the interface between the samples to the left, the bottom sample also pushes the interface to the left. The shear displacement is determined by measuring the movement of the aluminum plate that is placed between the samples. The lateral motion is measured with the LVDT probe shown touching the plate at the left of the figure. Besides providing a convenient measuring surface, the plate cancels out any symmetrical forces caused by the Poisson effect.

(Figure 5) The shear displacement of a stress-conversion MAC sample under compressive load.

The test results are shown in Figure 5 and indicate that the machines are working as expected. In this configuration, the strain is converted from compression to shear in an almost one-to-one ratio. The stress-conversion ratio, the elastic modulus, and the shear modulus of the MAC can be predetermined from the design of the machines and the properties of the starting materials.

The effect of the machine size on the displacement response of the MACs is measured using the previously discussed experimental device. Figure 6 shows the

shear versus compressive displacement MACs with three different-sized machines. The samples contained machines with a 60-degree inclination angle. The cross section of small, medium, and large machines were 1 mm, 1 cm, and 1.5 cm respectively. The 1 cm and 1.5 cm stress-conversion machines were manufactured using a rapid-prototyping device. The first thing to

notice is that the ratio of the shear to compressive displacement is approximately one to one. If the machine were a perfect four-bar linkage with hinges at the corners, simple geometry shows that ratio would have been 1.7 to one. The actual value is less than that because the machines act as a flexure, not as a hinge.

Figure 6 also shows that the samples containing the small, extruded machines respond with a slightly lower slope than the larger, rapid-prototype machines. The difference is not significant, considering that the size changed over an order of magnitude, and the machines themselves were made of two different polymers. The predominant effect may be due to the substantial fillet present in the extruded machines, as shown in Figure 3. The extrusion process tends to round corners, which show up as fillets in this machine design. In any case, the large machines represent the small machines quite well, allowing us to obtain the basic rules using the large machines.

(Figure 6) Shear vs. compressive displacements for MACS with different-sized machines with side-wall angles of 60-degrees.

Figure 7 shows a typical plot for the compressive-to-shear displacement behavior for samples made with the medium-sized machines. Again, the compressive-to-shear displacement ratio is approximately one to one. We also measured the properties of the medium sized machines without matrix. As shown in the figure, the samples without the matrix follows the same curve as the samples with the matrix. This result shows that the compression-to-shear conversion is purely a function of the geometry of the machines and not the machine/matrix volume ratio.

(Figure 7) Typical plot for a compressive displacement-to-shear displacement experiment using Z-type machine.

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS & ANALYTICAL MODELS

In this section, we present a finite-element analysis (FEA) model and an analytical model based on the theory of beam-on-elastic-foundation for a Machine Augmented Composite (MAC). The general model is first presented, and then a comparison of an analytical solution with the experimental and FEA results is presented.

Finite-element analysis solves the field equations of mechanical engineering to find the overall response of a structure. An important input to the FEA model is an accurate knowledge of the material's constitutive response as a fundamental material property measured independently in the lab.

The attraction of FEA is that it is possible to predict through "virtual experiments" the response of a structure before it is fabricated physically. Of course, any analysis, whether numerical or closed-formed, requires a model with simplification and approximations in order to make the problem tenable. The calculation of the virtual response is only worthwhile if the model's starting assumptions are validated at an early stage by comparison to an experimental result for a physical structure. Ideally, experiments and FEA calculations are actually complementary, not competitive, and proceed hand-in-hand to provide a problem's solution as quickly as possible.

Once established, however, the validation provides the confidence in calculations for structures too complicated or expensive to be tested experimentally. The validated model can also be used to quickly iterate over a design space to find a structure with optimal properties, a process that is otherwise much more costly and time consuming if physical structures must be built at each iteration.

DESCRIPTION OF THE FINITE-ELEMENT ANALYSIS

The Finite-Element Analysis was performed using ABAQUS. Quadratic, reduced integration elements were used in the analysis, with a hybrid formulation used to model the rubber. These elements were chosen in order to prevent hour-glassing and shear locking. For the constitutive formulation, the polymer machines were modeled as an elastic-plastic material, and the rubber matrix material was modeled as a non-linear elastic (hyper-elastic) material. The material constants used in the formulation were obtained from experimental tests. A two-dimensional plane strain model was used in the calculations. A plain stress formulation was also considered, yielding results very close to the results from the plain strain formulation.

RESULTS FROM THE FINITE-ELEMENT MODEL

Different MAC configurations were considered. Here we present some of the results for the 15-mm cross-section four-machine MACs with matrix material and a 60° inclination angle [3]. The undeformed state of the experimental specimen and the finite-element model are given in Figures 8a-8b. The deformed state of the experimental specimen and the deformed FEA model are shown in Figures 8c-8d. The FEA model clearly captures the deformation response of the experimental specimen. As shown in the experimental pictures from Figures 8a-8b and 8c-8d, vertical compression gives rise to lateral shearing.

(Figure 8c) Deformed state of experimental specimen.

(Figure 8b) Finite Element Model's undeformed mesh.

Finite Element Model's deformed mesh.

Figure 9 shows the experimental and FEA compressive versus shear displacements for the same MAC configuration. (MAC with matrix material and machines measuring 15 mm on a side with a 60° inclination angle). There is close agreement between FEA results and the experimental values, particularly for smaller displacements.

(Figure 9) Experimental and FEA results for the compressive displacement vs. shear displacement responses for MACs.

(Figure 10) Experimental, FEA and beam-on-elastic foundation analytical solution of the deformed state of the sidewall for MAC.

BEAM ON ELASTIC FOUNDATION ANALYTICAL MODEL

The theory of beam on elastic foundation can be used to obtain an analytical solution for the deformation of the MACs under compressive loading. The side-walls of each machine act like a beam on an elastic foundation that is provided by the matrix material. The closed form solution allows us to understand the influence that the different parameters have on the deformation pattern. The closed-form solution will also permit us to easily optimize the MAC design. The solution is given in reference [3].

Figure 10 shows the experimental, FEA and analytical deformed state of the sidewall of a large four-machine MAC with matrix material and a 60° inclination angle. The theoretical deformation pattern obtained from the theory of beams on elastic foundation captures very closely the actual deformation pattern obtained from the experiments, giving us confidence in the FEA model used and in the analytical solution obtained from the theory of beam-on-elastic-foundation.

CONCLUSIONS

A new type of composite material called Machine Augmented Composites (MAC) has been demonstrated that has unique properties and can be manufactured by embedding many small, passive, simple machines in a matrix. These simple machines modify the forces inside the material in a manner chosen by the material designer. When the machines are added to a traditional fiber reinforced composite, the fibers give the composite strength & stiffness while the machine adds additional properties thus providing enhanced functionality.

In this paper we have shown there is a very close match between the FEA results and the experimental results of the deformation behavior of MACs. The close match is observed in the global behavior of the MAC (shear versus compressive displacement of the whole MAC), as well as in the local behavior of the MAC (deformation pattern of the sidewalls of each individual machine embedded in the MAC).

We have also presented the deformation pattern of the sidewalls of the machines obtained from the theory of beam-on-elastic-foundation, which captures very closely the actual deformation pattern obtained from the experiments and FEA.

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